

A Study of Correlation of Serum Uric Acid Level and Severity of Pulmonary Hypertension

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Abstract:

Background: Pulmonary Hypertension is a chronic, progressive and a fatal disease. Gold standard test for diagnosis and clinical assessment of the patients with pulmonary hypertension is Right heart catheterisation. Recently the usefulness of cheaper and non-invasive tests in the follow-up of PH patients is being studied. The aim of the present study was to evaluate the relationship between serum uric acid levels and severity of pulmonary hypertension in PH patients.

Objective: To study the correlation between serum uric acid levels and severity of pulmonary hypertension and to study serum uric acid levels in pulmonary hypertension as an independent predictor of its severity.

Methods: Study was conducted in KIMS hubli on patients with clinical and echocardiographic features of Pulmonary Hypertension and total of 106 patients were included in the study based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. They were divided into 3 groups based on severity. Statistical analysis were conducted and results were drawn.

Result: Serum uric acid levels were found to be higher in pulmonary hypertension patients with severe Right Ventricular dysfunction, compared to mild and moderate dysfunction. Serum uric acid levels were significantly correlated with pulmonary arterial systolic pressure. Serum uric acid levels also had significant correlation with World Health Organization functional class of the patients.

Conclusion: From the study it can be concluded that serum Uric Acid levels are very well correlated with the severity of symptoms and right ventricular dysfunction in patients with pulmonary hypertension.

Keywords: Uric Acid; Severity; Pulmonary Hypertension.

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Introduction

Cardiovascular disease accounts for roughly 30% of deaths worldwide and is the leading cause of death globally [1]. In settings with limited resources, pulmonary vascular disease (PVD) is a significant contributor to the burden of cardiovascular disease. PVD broadly refers to any disorder that may affect the pulmonary blood circulation.

Pulmonary Hypertension (PH) is defined by a mean pulmonary artery (PA) pressure >25 mm Hg by invasive catheterization [2]. Approximately 98% of the global PVD burden occurs in the resource-limited world with an estimated prevalence of 20 to 25 million people with up to 64 million at risk but who are undiagnosed. Given this strikingly high statistic, and considering the associated morbidity and mortality, the recognition, treatment, and prevention of PVD in resource-limited areas is a

medical priority [3,4]. The disparity in the epidemiology of PVD between industrialized and resource-limited nations is significant. In resource-rich settings around the world, PH is due to heart failure in 55% of cases, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) in 42%, and PAH in only 3%. In resource-limited areas, heart failure accounts for 8% and COPD (and associated lung disorders) for 28% of PVD.

Schistosomiasis (18%), hematological disorders (7%), High Altitude (24%), rheumatic heart disease ([RHD] 11%), CHD (2%), and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) (1%) compose the other etiologies of PVD [3]. An increasing number of biomarkers have been described that are elevated in pulmonary hypertension and which may assist the clinician in diagnosis and in the assessment of disease severity and response to treatment. Such

biomarkers include Endothelin, Trop T, Natriuretic peptides, Uric acid, and Nitric oxide etc [5]. Uric acid is the final oxidation product of purine metabolism. Serum urate levels may be increased in conditions of impaired oxidative metabolism [5]. Several studies have demonstrated that an elevated urate level in PH correlates with severity of disease [7-8]. In one study, 90 patients with IPAH underwent right heart catheterisation and serum uric acid estimation, and were then followed for a mean of 31 months [8]. Serum urate was independently related to mortality on multivariate Cox proportional hazards analysis. Kaplan–Meier survival curves demonstrated that patients with high serum uric acid had a significantly higher mortality rate than those with low serum uric acid [8]. Serum uric acid is a non-invasive and inexpensive test that is widely available in all centers. Serum uric acid level has been shown to be increased in right or left heart failure [8]. Hyperuricemia is shown to have a strong correlation with the severity of symptoms and functional capacity of the patients with heart failure [9]. In this study, we aimed to evaluate the relationships between serum uric acid level and severity of symptoms and right ventricular (RV) dysfunction in patients with confirmed PH patients.

Material and Methods

This Prospective Observational study was conducted among patients presenting to KIMS, admitted in Medicine Department with clinical and echocardiographic features of Pulmonary Hypertension considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Duration of study was 2 years. Institutional ethical committee approval was obtained prior to the start of the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age above 18 years.
- Patients with clinical and echocardiographic features of Pulmonary Hypertension.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Renal Dysfunction
- Hepatic Diseases
- Thromboembolic Diseases
- Obstructive Pulmonary Diseases
- History of Interstitial Lung Diseases
- Congenital Cardiac Diseases
- Diabetes Mellitus

Sample size: 106 subjects with pulmonary hypertension were included in this study.

Sampling Method: Purposive sampling technique was adapted in the present to recruit the subjects. Patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were included during the study duration.

Methodology: Data was collected by using a Pre-tested Structured questionnaire method. All patients were subjected to detailed history, clinical examination and below mentioned laboratory investigations were done as per standard procedures

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered into Microsoft excel data sheet and was analyzed using SPSS 22 version software. Categorical data was represented in the form of Frequencies and proportions.

Chi-square test was used as test of significance for qualitative data. Continuous data was represented as mean and standard deviation.

Validity of test:

Screening test results	Diagnosis		Total
	Diseased	Healthy	
Positive	a (True positive)	b (False Postive)	a+b
Negative	c (False Negative)	d (True Negative)	c+d
Total	a + c	b + d	a+b+c+d

- Sensitivity = $a/(a+c) \times 100 = \text{True positive} / \text{True positive} + \text{False Negative}$
- Specificity = $d/(b+d) \times 100 = \text{True Negative} / \text{True Negative} + \text{False Postive}$
- Positive predictive value = $a/(a+b) \times 100 = \text{True Postive} / \text{True positive} + \text{False Postive}$
- Negative predictive value = $d/(c+d) \times 100 = \text{True Negative} / \text{True Negative} + \text{False Negative}$
- Diagnostic accuracy = $a + d / a + b + c + d = \text{True positive} + \text{True Negative} / \text{Total}$

P value (Probability that the result is true) of <0.05 was considered as statistically significant after assuming all the rules of statistical tests.

Results: The mean (SD) of Age (Years) was 49.37 (12.80). The median (IQR) of Age (Years) was 49.00 (42-57.75). The Age (Years) ranged from 26 - 76. The skewness of the data was 0.1, and it suggested that the data was not skewed, thus suggesting it was normally distributed. The kurtosis of the data was -0.89, and it suggested that the data was normally distributed. Shapiro-Wilk test for the data was significant (p = 0.033), suggesting that the data was not normally distributed. There appeared to be only one mode/peak in the data, thus making it unimodal. 8.5% of the participants had Age: 21-30 Years. 15.1% of the participants had Age: 31-40 Years. 32.1% of the participants had Age: 41-50 Years. 22.6% of the participants had Age: 51-60

Years. 16.0% of the participants had Age: 61-70
Years. 5.7% of the participants had Age: 71-80

Years. 34.9% of the participants had Gender: Male.
65.1% of the participants had Gender: Female.

Table 1: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of 'Diagnosis'

Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
Valvular Heart Disease	57	53.8%	43.9% - 63.4%
Ishchemic Heart Disease	34	32.1%	23.5% - 41.9%
Bronchiectasis	6	5.7%	2.3% - 12.4%
Obstructive Sleep Apnea	4	3.8%	1.2% - 9.9%
SLE	3	2.8%	0.7% - 8.7%
MCTD	2	1.9%	0.3% - 7.3%

53.8% of the participants had Diagnosis: Valvular Heart Disease. 32.1% of the participants had Diagnosis: Ishchemic Heart Disease. 5.7% of the participants had Diagnosis: Bronchiectasis. 3.8% of the participants had Diagnosis: Obstructive Sleep Apnea. 2.8% of the participants had Diagnosis: SLE. 1.9% of the participants had.

Table 2: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of 'NYHA Class'

NYHA Class	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
I	14	13.2%	7.7% - 21.5%
II	21	19.8%	12.9% - 28.9%
III	25	23.6%	16.1% - 33.0%
IV	46	43.4%	33.9% - 53.4%

13.2% of the participants had NYHA Class: I. 19.8% of the participants had NYHA Class: II. 23.6% of the participants had NYHA Class: III. 43.4% of the participants had NYHA Class: IV.

Table 3: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of '2D ECHO-PASP'

2D ECHO-PASP (mmHg)	
Mean (SD)	72.92 (19.89)
Median (IQR)	75 (55-90)
Range	38 - 125

The mean (SD) of 2D ECHO-PASP (mmHg) was 72.92 (19.89). The median (IQR) of 2D ECHO-PASP (mmHg) was 75.00 (55-90). The 2D ECHO-PASP (mmHg) ranged from 38 - 125. The skewness of the data was -0.07, and it suggested that the data was not skewed, thus suggesting it was normally distributed.

Table 4: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of '6MWD (meter)'

6MWD (meter)	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
<200	71	67.0%	57.1% - 75.6%
200-400	20	18.9%	12.2% - 27.9%
>400	15	14.2%	8.4% - 22.6%

67.0% of the participants had 6MWD (meter) : <200. 18.9% of the participants had 6MWD (meter): 200-400. 14.2% of the participants had 6MWD (meter) : >400.

Table 5: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of 'S. Uric Acid (mg/dL)'

S. Uric Acid (mg/dL)	
Mean (SD)	7.72 (1.91)
Median (IQR)	7.75 (6.53-8.95)
Range	3.8 - 13.2

The mean (SD) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) was 7.72 (1.91). The median (IQR) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) was 7.75 (6.53-8.95). The S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ranged from 3.8 - 13.2.

Table 6: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of 'Severity of Pulmonary Hypertension'

Severity of Pulmonary Hypertension	Frequency	Percentage	95% CI
Mild	14	13.2%	7.7% - 21.5%
Moderate	21	19.8%	12.9% - 28.9%
Severe	71	67.0%	57.1% - 75.6%

In the present study patients with pulmonary hypertension were divided into 3 categories based on pulmonary arterial systolic pressure (PASP) values as MILD (36- 45mmHg), MODERATE (46-60mmHg) and SEVERE(>60mmHg). In present study 14(13.2%) participant's belonged to mild category, 21(19.8%) participants belonged to the moderate category and 71(67%) participants belonged to the severe category.

Table 6: Distribution of the Participants in Terms of 'D Dimer (ng/mL)'

D Dimer (ng/mL)	
Mean (SD)	916.12 (243.14)
Median (IQR)	880 (753.25-993.75)
Range	500 - 1800

The mean (SD) of D Dimer (ng/mL) was 916.12 (243.14). The median (IQR) of D Dimer (ng/mL) was 880.00 (753.25-993.75). The D Dimer (ng/mL) ranged from 500 - 1800. The skewness of the data was 1.05, and it suggested that the data was positively skewed, thus suggesting it was not normally distributed. The kurtosis of the data was 1.48, and it suggested that the data was normally distributed. Shapiro-Wilk test for the data was significant ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that the data was not normally distributed. There appeared to be only one mode/peak in the data, thus making it unimodal.

The mean (SD) of D Dimer (ng/mL) in Mild group was 638.57 (79.25). The mean (SD) of D Dimer (ng/mL) in Moderate group was 742.10 (100.59). The mean (SD) of D Dimer (ng/mL) in Severe group was 1022.32 (220.65).

There was no statistically significant correlation between Age (Years) and S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ($r = 0.02$, $p = 0.874$). There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ($t = 0.535$, $p = 0.59$). The variable S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) was not normally distributed in the 6 subgroups of the variable Diagnosis.

The mean (SD) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Valvular Heart Disease group was 7.59 (1.96). The mean (SD) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Ischemic Heart Disease group was 7.89 (1.61). The mean (SD) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Bronchiectasis group was 7.80 (2.28). The mean (SD) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Obstructive Sleep Apnea group was 8.80 (3.61).

The mean (SD) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: SLE group was 7.63 (1.53). The mean (SD) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis:

MCTD group was 6.60 (1.84). The median (IQR) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Valvular Heart Disease group was 7.7 (6.3-8.7). The median (IQR) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Ischemic Heart Disease group was 7.7 (6.73-9.1). The median (IQR) of

S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Bronchiectasis group was 8 (7.35-9.03). The median (IQR) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Obstructive Sleep Apnea group was 8.65 (6.4-11.05). The median (IQR) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: SLE group was 7.3 (6.8-8.3). The median (IQR) of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: MCTD group was 6.6 (5.95-7.25). The S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Valvular Heart Disease ranged from 4.2 - 13.2. The S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Ischemic Heart Disease ranged from 5.1 - 11.2. The S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Bronchiectasis ranged from 3.8 - 10.5. The S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: Obstructive Sleep Apnea ranged from 4.9 - 13. The S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: SLE ranged from 6.3 - 9.3. The S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in the Diagnosis: MCTD ranged from 5.3 - 7.9.

There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ($\chi^2 = 1.611$, $p = 0.900$).

Individual points represent individual cases. The blue trendline represents the general trend of correlation between the two variables. The shaded grey area represents the 95% confidence interval of this trendline.

There was a moderate negative correlation between SpO2 (%) and S. Uric Acid (mg/dL), and this correlation was statistically significant ($\rho = -0.53$, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 1: Scatterplot depicting correlation between Spo2 (%) and S. Uric acid levels

The blue trendline represents the general trend of correlation between the two variables. The shaded grey area represents the 95% confidence interval of this trendline.

There was a moderate positive correlation between Respiratory Rate (CPM) and S. Uric Acid (mg/dL), and this correlation was statistically significant ($\rho = 0.47, p < 0.001$).

The variable S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) was normally distributed in the 2 subgroups of the variable Smoking History.

There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ($t = -0.025, p = 0.980$). The variable S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) was normally distributed in the 2 subgroups of the variable Alcohol History.

There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ($t = 0.758, p = 0.456$). The correlation between 2D ECHO-PASP (mmHg) and S. Uric Acid (mg/dL). Individual points represent individual cases. The blue trendline represents the general trend of correlation between the two variables. The shaded grey area represents the 95% confidence interval of this trendline. There was a strong positive correlation between 2D ECHO-PASP (mmHg) and S.Uric Ac-

id (mg/dL), and this correlation was statistically significant ($\rho = 0.87, p < 0.001$)

There was a significant difference between the 3 groups in terms of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ($\chi^2 = 60.507, p < 0.001$), with the median S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) being highest in the Severity of Pulmonary Hypertension: Severe group.

The variable S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) was not normally distributed in the 3 subgroups of the variable 6MWD (meter).

There was a significant difference between the 3 groups in terms of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ($\chi^2 = 60.498, p < 0.001$), with the median S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) being highest in the 6MWD (meter) : <200 group.

The variable S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) was not normally distributed in the 4 subgroups of the variable NYHA Class. Thus, non-parametric tests (Kruskal Wallis Test) were used to make group comparisons.

There was a significant difference between the 4 groups in terms of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ($\chi^2 = 69.861, p < 0.001$), with the median S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) being highest in the NYHA Class: IV group.

Primary Diagnostic Parameters

Variable	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Diagnostic Accuracy
S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) (Cutoff: 6.1 by ROC)	92.4% (85-97)	85.7% (57-98)	97.7% (92-100)	63.2% (38-84)	91.5% (84-96)

Figure 2: ROC Curve Analysis Showing Diagnostic Performance of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) in Predicting Severity of Pulmonary Hypertension

The area under the ROC curve (AUROC) for S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) predicting moderate to severe cases of Pulmonary Hypertension when compared to mild cases was 0.951 (95% CI: 0.906 - 0.996), thus demonstrating excellent diagnostic performance. It was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). At a cutoff of S. Uric Acid (mg/dL) ≥ 6.1 mg/dl, it predicts moderate to severe cases of Pulmonary Hypertension when compared to mild cases with a sensitivity of 92%, and a specificity of 86%.

Discussion:

In the present study which is a single center, prospective observational study, the primary objective was to study the uric acid levels in patients with pulmonary hypertension in predicting its severity. We also studied correlation of serum uric acid levels with NYHA class and 6MWD.

Among the 106 patients who were included in this study had varied presentation and they were studied by dividing them into 3 severity groups namely mild 14(13.2%), moderate 16(15.1%) and severe 76(71.1%) based on PASP values obtained from 2D echo. Study subjects were also studied by determining which WHO functional class they belong to namely NYHA I 14(13.20%), NYHA II 21(19.8%), NYHA III 25(23.6%) and NYHA IV 46(43.4%).

Seyyed Reza Seyyedi et al [10] in their study demonstrated that serum uric acid was significantly correlated with pulmonary artery systolic pressure and serum uric acid level also had a significant positive correlation with the World Health Organi-

zation functional class of the patients. Nagaraju Boyilla et al [11] in their study demonstrated that hyperuricemia is common in patients with severe PH and there is strong correlation between the elevated uric acid levels and mortality among patients and the NYHA class. They also suggested that the uric acid levels can be a guide to predict the pulmonary hypertension thereby initiating timely treatment to the patient.

Noritoshi Nagaya et al [12] in their study demonstrated that serum UA levels were elevated in patients with PPH, and serum UA levels negatively correlated with cardiac output and positively correlated with total pulmonary resistance. They also demonstrated that serum UA levels decreased in association with a reduction of total pulmonary resistance during vasodilator therapy and among non-invasive variables, serum UA was independently related to the mortality by a multivariate analysis, and that patients with high serum UA levels had a significantly lower survival rate than did those with low serum UA levels, from the Kaplan-Meier survival curves according to the median value of UA for each sex.

C Zang et al [13] in their study demonstrated that the serum levels of uric acid in patients with IPAH were higher than in the healthy subjects and there was a positive correlation between uric acid levels and the MPAP; and there was an inverse correlation between uric acid levels and right ventricular function. Mean serum uric acid level was 7.72 ± 1.91 mg/dl. In Seyyed Reza Seyyedi et al study mean serum uric acid level was 5.83mg/dl. In Nor-

itoshi Nagaya et al study mean serum uric acid level was 7.5 ± 2.5 mg/dl. In Nagaraju Boyilla et al study mean serum uric acid level was 7.1 ± 2.6 mg/dl. In Seyyed Reza Seyyedi et al study 16(14.5%) belonged to NYHA I, 25(22.7%) belonged to NYHA II, 29(26.4%) belonged to NYHA III, 40(36.4%) belonged to NYHA IV. In Noritoshi Nagaya et al study 5(6%) belonged to NYHA II, 72(80%) belonged to NYHA III, 13(14%) belonged to NYHA IV.

In comparison with respect to mean uric acid levels in different NYHA functional classes, In present study mean uric acid level was 5.15 ± 0.86 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class I, 6.27 ± 0.91 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class II, 7.74 ± 1.07 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class III, and 9.16 ± 1.47 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class IV. In Seyyed Reza Seyyedi et al mean uric acid level was 4.70 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class I & II, 5 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class III, and 7.80 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class IV. In Noritoshi Nagaya et al study mean uric acid level was 5 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class I, 4.9 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class II, 9.2 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class III, and 11.9 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class IV. In C Zang et al study mean uric acid level was 5.85 ± 1.18 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class II, 6.99 ± 2.12 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class III, and 10.26 ± 2.47 mg/dl in subjects belonging to NYHA class IV.

In Seyyed Reza Seyyedi et al study mean serum uric acid levels mild, moderate and severe pulmonary hypertension groups were 4.70 mg/dl, 5 mg/dl and 7.80 mg/dl respectively. Present study was comparable to Seyyed Reza Seyyedi et al study as both studies showed significant positive correlation of serum uric acid levels with pulmonary artery systolic pressure.

Conclusion:

Serum Uric acid levels were found to be significantly elevated in patients with pulmonary hypertension. It strongly correlates with severity of pulmonary hypertension as determined by pulmonary artery systolic pressure (PASP). It also correlates with NYHA functional class and 6 minute walk distance in patients with pulmonary hypertension. At a cut off of 6.1 mg/dl it predicts moderate to severe cases of pulmonary hypertension when compared to mild cases with sensitivity of 92% and specificity of 80%.

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